

USMAN NASIR'S LIFE PATH AND CREATIVE LEGACY: ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH

Urinov Odilbek Laziz o'g'li

is a teacher at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
Republic of Uzbekistan

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Introduction Usman Nasir's poetry, first of all, has a deep place in the reader's heart due to its vitality, attractiveness and rebelliousness, and at the same time, its simplicity and fluency. That is probably why the poet's poems are still often mentioned in circles: Usman Nasir, a talented poet who became prominent and popular in the 1930s, was born on November 13, 1912 in the city of Namangan. After graduating from secondary school, Usman, who spent his youth in an orphanage in Kokand, studied at the language and literature faculty of Samarkand Pedagogical Academy named after Alisher Navoi together with Amin Umariy and Adham Hamdam from 1931. Usman Nasir's first poems were written in school it started to appear in the press when he was still young. The poet's poetry collections such as "Quyosh bilan suhbat" (1932), "Safarbar satlar" (1932), "Tractorabad" (1934), "Yurak" (1935), "Mehrim" (1936), "Norbota" " and "Nakhshon" epics were published one after another.¹⁴⁹

Main part

Although Usman Nasir entered the world of literature at a very young age, he was able to prove that he is a mature artist with his own words and voice. History itself is witness to the fact that every poem of the poet reached the hearts of lovers of creativity like the voice of his fiery heart, and a light example shone in the language of millions. His work is of great importance for the students of his time and today. The following words of the well-known literary critic, scientist, translator and critic Ibrahim Ghafurov are a clear proof of our opinion: "We have an inexhaustible debt to Usman Nasir. Every

¹⁴⁹ O'tkir Rashid. Literature textbook for 8th grade part 2.

time he remembers Usman Nasir, every time he enjoys his words - his poems and epics, this debt is always held by a person's shoulder like a hand extended from a mosque.

Discussion and results

His work "Norbota" (1932) the theme of the civil war in Uzbekistan was sung, in "Nakhshon" the aspirations of the children of the brotherly Armenian people for freedom were sung, while the struggle of slaves in the ancient world was reflected in poetic works such as "Nile and Rome". Usman Nasir's poem "Heart" is one of the poems that embody the poet's human character and creative destiny. The poet considers the image of the heart to be the embodiment of his inspiration, creative aspirations, feelings, and dreams. That is, his appeal to the Heart actually sounds like an appeal to his personality and creativity. Besides, when we read the poem "The Wayfarer", a true admirer will surely notice something. Even if he is a lyrical hero, the poet is not a person who lives in dreams that can be achieved like most ordinary people. His desired destination requires "running with intent". To reach these destinations, he will have to work hard and face many violent storms... I am sure that the human child has been wounded and has been fighting against slavery, arbitrariness and dumbness. The fate of people who passed thousands of years before him is no stranger to the poet, who is a child of man by nature. He sees every victim of tyranny as his own, and asks the oppressors for their food.¹⁵⁰ This poem sounds like Usman Nasir's rebellion against the heavy freedom and darkness of exile that awaits him! Usman Nasir also gave the formula of this truth in his work and sought the solution from history and today.

Both the past, the present, and the future became the subject of his charming poems. He compared the tragedy of the poor and slaves oppressed by oppression and tyranny in the past with the system of his time. "I will suffer, reach, I am oblivious", he says sadly. We discussed about Usman Nasir and the time he lived in our previous lessons. There is another source of inspiration that opens the mind of the creator and causes new debates, without which we cannot fully understand the poetry of Usman Nasir. The poem was written on the 23rd of spring, and it is "Nile and Rome" (6 stanzas = 14 stanzas each = 84 lines). Usman Nasir eagerly studied not only literature, but also world history, philosophy, and art. He was in a hurry to learn and create following the greats. Therefore, his writings clearly reflected great ideas, free flights of artistic thinking, and sharp flames of thought.¹⁵¹

Uzbek writer Abdulla Oripov says about Usman Nasir: "Who do we mean by Usman Nasir?" He has such a talent that he is a fire that burns wherever he touches. Usman Nasir is the dew that has not yet flowed from the fountain of great and eternal poetry. It is a half-smile that remains forever on our lips without turning into laughter. His poems are alive, vibrant, and irresistible.

¹⁵⁰Murodova M. I am a small fragment of the era. ziyouz.uz electronic site // Fitna

¹⁵¹Mejdunarodniy nauchniy zhurnal No. 3(100), chapter 1 «Scientific impulse» October, 2022.

We appreciate Usman Nasir. Because he has created a miraculous garden in the blessed and holy place of poetry, which cannot be described as a miracle " - in order to prove this definition expressed by Abdulla Oripov, we quote this verse from the poet's language:

The heart burns like a fire,
I am happy if I can fight.

Fire, which is a clear proof of how passionate and inexhaustible courage Usman Nasir is. That is why Abdulla Oripov describes Usman Nasir as "He is a fire that burns the place it touches." In the second stanza of this poem, Usman considers it a happiness to enter the battles if it benefits the country, people, society, and humanity of Nasir. This is also a bright expression of the poet's high human qualities. As a continuation of our opinion, we pay attention to the poet's poem "Heart", his appeal to his own heart:

Obey!
If from you
the country does not agree,
Crack, turn into lightning,
Crack! Well, if I die!

In this poem, Usman Nasir always takes the reins of his stubborn heart and urges him to obey. There is only one reason for this, and that is the approval of the country. If the country does not agree, he insists that he is willing to crack and turn into lightning, even if it causes his death. If you think about it, why does the poet want his heart to turn into lightning, why not into a star or wind, but lightning? Because lightning is a miracle. It is understood that ¹⁵² Usman Nasir also wants to remain in people's memory as the same lightning. We all know that the poet's wish has come true. The scales of my youth are free, is heavy with spring stone. My joy is great, my joy is great... I am speechless, seen such youth. is weighed down with a "spring stone", as it is known, the other side is weighed down by the burden of injustices and sufferings done to it. Forgetting the other side of the scale, the poet says, "My joy is great, my joy is great... my tongue is full of joy", he gives thanks, saying "what life has seen such youth " and proves his point. As Usman Nasir's poems are written with finger weight, the poet skillfully uses all poetic arts. Usman Nasir's poems "Nile and Rim", "Monologue", "Let's go to the mountains ", "Have you walked together with the moon", "Moonlight nights...", "My child" are huge. it is considered a poetic miracle and sometimes makes people laugh and sometimes cry. Sometimes it sinks into the world of suffering, sometimes it makes you think and takes it far away.

This poem stirs the emotions of the reader. Excitement frees a person from indifference. A poem that can save someone from indifference is an example of original

¹⁵² <https://zenodo.org/record> . Rayhona Bakhtiyorova

artistry. Usman Nasir's "Yana She'rimga"(Again to my poem) is one of the poems that define his creative image. Having read this poem carefully, the poet understands the reason why the poet lost his young life by writing such works, not bowing down to the demands of the unjust times. In the poem, it is very beautifully and succinctly expressed that a real work is the product of great pain:

A fire in a body that has no love?

I'm sorry, my poem, you're fine.

According to Usman Nasir, poetry is not a pastime. He is a "person of life". Poetry has its own life, its own existence. In order to create poems with his own life, the poet agrees to "spit blood in the morning". In the poem "What I Said to Nasima" Usman Nasir impressively expresses his purpose in a highly artistic form. The poet, who believes that "I have a lot of luck in my life", feels that there are difficult trials ahead of him. The poet's alarming prediction is expressed as follows:

I have an exam ahead of me

I will be in tough battles.

Nasima! Today's hot blood,

Oh, maybe it'll spill... I'll die...

Thirsty for struggles, ready for battles, the burning heart of a person who is more than death is very impressively expressed in this poem. Osman Nasir considered Cholpon to be his greatest teacher. Although there is a lot of spiritual affinity in their poems, the external similarity is not strong. Cholpon's poems are very gentle. The most disturbing feelings, the fiercest protests are written in poetry with oriental tenderness and Uzbek musicality. A different situation can be observed in Usman Nasir. It reflects hot feelings, intense mental states in a way that excites a person. At the end of the poem, he does not restrain himself. His poems are artistic documents that clearly show the personality of their authors.

Summary

In all his poems and translations, there are lines and clauses that have entered the destiny language! Maybe destiny entered his heart very early. But the voice of fate began to be heard in his poems from the thirty-third year without stopping. Do you remember the last lines of his program poem "Heart": "*Crack, turn into lightning, Crack!*" *It's okay if I die!..* » I consider this to be the voice of fate. The poet went on to predict his own fate. Or remember the famous "Monologue". In this case, all grassy lines are the voice of destiny. And especially: "*Perhaps, without finishing - My life will end...*" Apparently, "Nile and Rome" is also a fate from head to toe. "*My lamp is burning... a heavy Thought like a wounded wing presses on. It's like a flood in my heart...*" Usman Nasir's argument with Homer in this mysterious poem, fighting a tiger with a gladiator on the Roman stage, the people's enjoyment of this bloody scene, and

finally, " *Rome is death from the game The crazy theater that was waiting for him* was also a prophecy of his fate.

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